

Differentiation of Mixtures of Amines by Conductometric Titration in Glycolic Media*

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Mixtures of bases have been differentiated by conductometric titration in propylene glycol and in glycol-chloroform mixtures of varying compositions. The effect of chloroform on the sharpness of differentiation has been studied. Chloroform impairs the break for the neutralisation of the weakest base (e.g., pyridine) in the mixture, but accentuates the sharpness of the breaks for the stronger bases. As many as four breaks in the titration curves have been obtained, e.g., for a mixture containing piperidine, ethylenediamine, triethanolamine and pyridine.

Glycolic media (ethylene glycol or propylene glycol preferably mixed with a suitable co-solvent), first proposed by Palit¹, have been widely used²⁻¹² for the titration of various weak bases including salts of weak acids, and also for the differentiation of acid mixtures by potentiometric titration. Das¹³ used propylene glycol-chloroform media for differentiating titration (potentiometric) of several base mixtures like piperidine-pyridine, piperazine-piperidine, piperazine-pyridine, etc. In view of these observations and of the distinct advantages of glycolic solvents as titration media, further investigations were undertaken on the differentiation of bases by glycolic titration.

In the work presented here, the solvent media used consisted of propylene glycol and chloroform mixed in different proportions, and differentiating titrations of some bases in the mixtures have been carried out conductometrically. The bases chosen had pK_b values close enough in water, but it must be pointed out that several cases of reversal of relative base strengths have been observed in going over from water to glycolic media^{14, 15}. The object of the present study was mainly qualitative, and precise determination of the concentrations of the bases in the mixtures was not attempted.

EXPERIMENTAL

Piperidine, monoethanolamine, triethanolamine, α -picoline, pyridine, and ethylenediamine were of analytical reagent grade (Merck or Riedel), and were used without any further treatment. Aniline (B.D.H.) was kept over pellets of potassium hydroxide for several hours, decanted and then distilled in an all glass distilling apparatus.

Chloroform and propylene glycol were of analytical reagent grade (B.D.H.), and were checked for the absence of acidic or basic impurities.

A conductivity bridge (Philips) was used for recording conductance.

* Dedicated to Prof. Santi R. Palit on the occasion of his 60th birth anniversary.

Solutions : Hydrochloric acid solutions of concentration of approximately 0.2*N* were prepared in different solvents namely, pure propylene glycol and four other mixed solvents in which the proportions of propylene glycol and chloroform were 2 : 1, 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3. Though the precise concentrations of the acids were not needed for the work, their strengths were determined by titrating against sodium acetate solution of known concentration in the same solvent as that of the acid, using thymol blue as the indicator.

Bases : Separate solutions of bases of concentration 0.1*M* each were prepared in pure propylene glycol. Their strengths were known by titrating against hydrochloric acid of known concentration in the same solvent using thymol blue as the indicator.

Procedure : Measured volumes of different bases in propylene glycol were pipetted into a beaker (capacity 150 ml). For exact quantitative work a pipette should not, however, be used to transfer glycolic solutions. But since the present work is of a qualitative or semiquantitative nature, pipetting is permissible. The mixture was then diluted with propylene glycol alone or a mixture of propylene glycol and chloroform so that the final volume contained the desired ratio for the concentrations of the constituents of the mixed solvent. The concentration of each base in the diluted solution was approximately 0.01*M*. The solution was conductometrically titrated with approximately 0.2*N* hydrochloric acid in the solvent having the same composition as that of the solution of the bases.

When the titration was carried out in pure propylene glycol, the acid from the burette was added drop by drop to avoid drainage error. In the case of the mixed solvent, however, there was no such difficulty. When the mixed solvent contained high chloroform content, as high as three times that of propylene glycol, a slight change in the concentration of acid and the bases in the titration vessel may occur because of the evaporation of chloroform due to its high volatility. This was not, however, a very important factor in the present semi-quantitative work. Nevertheless, the strength of hydrochloric acid solution was checked frequently and the titration was carried out in a tall beaker covering the top as far as possible.

RESULTS

Titration of different bases in mixtures were carried out in various solvents and the curves obtained are shown in Figures 1-6.

Figure 1 shows four curves obtained in the titration of 50 ml ethylenediamine (0.01*M*) with 0.02*N* hydrochloric acid in various solvents ranging from pure propylene glycol to a mixed solvent having propylene glycol and chloroform in the proportion of 1 : 3. Two breaks were obtained in all the titrations due to the two basic nitrogen atoms contained in the base. The difference in their pK_b values (in water) is 3.09. In pure propylene glycol alone, after the first break, the middle portion of the titration curve has a positive slope whereas with a higher content of chloroform in the mixed solvent, the middle line shows a negative slope. At a still higher concentration, the line has practically zero slope, indicating that there is very little change in conductance during the neutralisation of the second nitrogen in ethylene diamine. This presumably arises because of the formation of ion pairs, which should become predominant in this medium because of the decreased dielectric

constant. In pure glycol, however, the conductance increases during the second neutralisation as might be expected, since ion pair formation should not occur to such a predominant extent in this medium. The sharpest breaks were obtained with 1 : 1 composition of the

Fig. 1. Titration of a solution of Ethylenediamine.

Propylene glycol : Chloroform

1	1	:	0
2	1	:	1
3	1	:	2
4	1	:	3

mixed solvent, whereas with higher contents of chloroform, the conductance of the solution as a whole decreased making the measurements more difficult and the breaks less sharp.

Figure 2 shows curves obtained in the titration of 50 ml of the solution containing piperidine (0.01M) and ethylenediamine (0.01M). Three definable breaks were obtained when the solvent used was pure propylene glycol. Breaks were the sharpest in the mixed solvent (1 : 1). Here, the first break corresponds to the neutralisation of piperidine ($pK_b = 2.88$ in water). The difference between pK_b value of the stronger base piperidine and that of the first basic nitrogen ($pK_b = 3.91$ in water) of ethylenediamine is only 1.03.

Figure 3 shows the titration curve for a mixture (100 ml) containing piperidine ($pK_b = 2.88$ in water), ethylenediamine (3.91 and 9.00) and pyridine. Their respective concentrations in the solution were 0.007M, 0.005M and 0.008M. Curves 1, 3 and 4 were obtained on titration of the solutions containing bases of the above concentrations. For curve 2, the concentrations of the bases taken in the solution were 0.008M, 0.006M and 0.007M respectively. When the mixed solvent contained propylene glycol and chloroform

in the proportion 2 : 1 and 1 : 1, four definable breaks were obtained. In propylene glycol alone, the first break due to piperidine was not sharp enough, whereas in the solvent which was relatively rich in chloroform (1 : 2), the last break due to pyridine was not at all discernible. In fact, this last break deteriorated as the mixed solvent contained more and more

Fig. 2. Titration of a solution containing Ethylenediamine and Piperidine
Propylene glycol : Chloroform

1	1	:	0
2	1	:	1
3	1	:	2
4	1	:	3

chloroform. It can, however, be seen that the addition of chloroform in the solvent increases the sharpness of the first break. The best medium for the differentiation of all the four bases contained in this particular mixture is the mixed solvent containing propylene glycol and chloroform in the proportion 1 : 1 or 2 : 1.

A mixture (100 ml) containing piperidine (0.007M), ethylene diamine (0.005M), triethanolamine (0.004M) and pyridine (0.004M) was titrated. The titration curve obtained is shown in the Figure 4. A single titration in the mixed solvent containing propylene glycol and chloroform in the ratio 2 : 1 was carried out. The curve shows four definable

breaks. The first break is due to the piperidine content, the second one is due to the first basic nitrogen of ethylenediamine, the third one (which shows some off points) is due to the total of triethanolamine ($pK_b = 6.23$ in water) and the second basic nitrogen ($pK_b = 7.0$ in water) of ethylenediamine. The fourth break is due to the weakest base pyridine.

Fig. 3. Titration of a solution containing Piperidine, Ethylenediamine and Pyridine
Propylene glycol : Chloroform

1	1	:	0
2	2	:	1
3	1	:	1
4	1	:	2

Figure 5 shows the titration curve for a solution containing piperidine ($0.006M$), monoethanolamine ($0.005M$), triethanolamine ($0.004M$) and pyridine ($0.004M$). A single titration of the above mixture was carried out in the mixed solvent propylene glycol-chloroform 2 : 1. Four breaks corresponding to the four bases present were obtained, although the breaks were not as sharp as for the previous mixtures. As stated earlier, a higher chloroform content in the solvent decreases the sharpness of the break due to the weakest base pyridine. Titration of another mixture (100 ml) containing the same bases (concentrations being $0.005M$, $0.004M$, $0.005M$ and $0.006M$ respectively) was also carried out. The corresponding curve is included in Figure 5. The titration was carried out in the medium 2 : 1

Fig. 4. Titration of a solution containing Piperidine, Ethylenediamine, Triethanolamine and Pyridine

Fig. 5. Titration of a solution containing Piperidine, Monoethanolamine, Triethanolamine and Pyridine.
Propylene glycol : Chloroform
1 : 2 : 1

propylene glycol-chloroform, because the chloroform content helps in giving a more definable break for pipelidine. The titration was continued up to about half neutralization of pyridine, i.e., some way beyond the third break. Thereafter, propylene glycol was added, so that the medium now became nearly 5 : 1 propylene glycol-chloroform. On now completing the titration, a better break for pyridine was obtained. On dilution with glycol, there naturally occurs a sharp fall in conductance and on continuing the titration, a separate titration curve is obtained, the break corresponding to the neutralization of pyridine.

Results of the titration of mixtures containing α -picoline ($pK_b = 7.98$ in water) and aniline ($pK_b = 9.40$ in water) are given in Figure 6. Curves (1) and (2) show the results of the titration in pure propylene glycol of solutions (100 ml) in which the concentration of α -picoline and aniline were $0.006M$ and $0.004M$ respectively. In both the curves, the first break due to α -picoline was not sharp. However, on carrying out the titration in the medium of 2 : 1 propylene glycol-chloroform the first break becomes slightly sharper.

Fig. 6. The titration of a solution containing α -picoline and Aniline
Propylene glycol : Chloroform

1	1	:	0
2	1	:	0
3	2	:	1

The general features of the results for the differentiating conductometric titration of the mixtures of bases are summarised in Table 1. The results indicate that propylene glycol-chloroform media are eminently suitable for the differentiation of mixtures of bases by conductometric titration. In actual analysis, it may sometimes be advantageous to perform separate titrations with the base mixture using solvent media of different compositions, so as to accentuate the various breaks all of which may not be accurately located by titrating in a single medium.

TABLE 1

Conductometric titration of mixtures of bases in pure propylene glycol and chloroform-propylene glycol media

Base	Medium	Nature of breaks
1. Ethylenediamine	Propylene glycol	2 sharp breaks with positive slopes.
2. -do-	Propylene glycol : Chloroform 2 : 1 1 : 1 1 : 2 1 : 3	2 breaks, pronounced; second line has negative slope. Breaks less pronounced than in pure glycol.
3. Piperidine + Ethylenediamine	Propylene glycol Propylene glycol + Chloroform 1 : 1 1 : 2 1 : 3	Three definable breaks Three sharp, breaks. 1st break sharper than in pure glycol. Breaks are less sharp.
4. Piperidine + Ethylenediamine + Pyridine	Propylene glycol Propylene glycol + Chloroform 2 : 1 Higher chloroform content	Four breaks definable. Four sharp breaks. Last break becomes indefinable.
5. Piperidine + Ethylenediamine + Triethanolamine + Pyridine.	Propylene glycol + Chloroform 2 : 1	Four definable breaks. Triethanolamine and second basic nitrogen of Ethylenediamine appear to have only one break.
6. Piperidine + Monoethanolamine + Triethanolamine + Pyridine.	2 : 1	Four definable breaks but not as sharp as in the case of mixture 4.
7. α -picoline + aniline	Propylene glycol Propylene glycol + Chloroform 2 : 1	2 definable breaks. 2 definable breaks, more sharp.

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